

European Researchers' Night 2024/25

Communication Report D6.1. Awareness Campaign 2025

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1. | Executive Summary

The European Researchers' Night (ERN) is an initiative promoted and funded by the European Commission under the Horizon Europe Programme and European Research Executive Agency. The 2024/25 ERN project, called EU-EMBRACES - Empowering Minds: Boosting Research in Citizen Engagement and Schools, arises from the consortium coordinated by Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica António Xavier - ITQB NOVA, together with the Institute for Research and Innovation in Health - i3S, and the Ciência Viva Network. This consortium, based in Portugal, aims to bridge the gap between researchers and the public, fostering curiosity, understanding, and appreciation for scientific research and the EU-Missions.

With the support from the European Union, the event was hosted in 9 cities across Portugal, drawing participants from diverse backgrounds, including students, families and educators. The event showcased hands-on activities, interactive science exhibitions, and engaging lectures, all designed to demystify scientific concepts and celebrate the vital role of research in society.

The ERN 2025 awareness campaign was designed to maximise both visibility and engagement, targeting a broad audience through diverse media channels, social media platforms and direct partnerships. The strategy integrated multi-channel promotions and leveraged both digital and traditional media to build public interest and drive attention. Social media platforms each played a key role in connecting with specific audience segments, while the official ERN website provided centralised information and updates on all event activities. Additionally, collaborations with national and regional media, including newspapers and podcasts, extended our reach, establishing European Researchers' Night as a celebrated event across Portugal.

Key Outcomes and Highlights

- **High reach:** The ERN Project generated significant interest across media channels, with coverage in over 30 major channels, including television, radio, newspapers and online publications. Some of these were Público (digital newspaper with more than **54000** paid subscriptions), CMTV (TV channel which had **6,2%** of the total audience shares in September 2025) and SIC (TV channel which had **14,6%** of the total audience share in September 2025). An ad promoting ERN was broadcast on RTP2 and RTP3 – Rádio e Televisão de Portugal channels – and on Antena 1 – one of RTP's public radio channels. Digital campaigns reached approximately **103000** users on social media and **18700** unique visitors on the website. Furthermore, more than **11500** people were made aware of ERN by participating in the **31** build-up activities organised by all venues of this consortium. To add to the overall reach of the national communication efforts, each venue developed a local awareness campaign that complemented the first.
- **Collaborative approach to social media dissemination:** On social media, especially Instagram, we prioritized a collaborative strategy, with approximately **28** posts created in collaboration with partners, institutions, and public figures, leveraging the reach of our initiatives. This was possible by combining the know-how of the three partners to build a content plan together.
- **Other collaborative Efforts:** The project brought together more than **800** researchers from several academic institutions, research centres and associations across Portugal. It fostered networking opportunities and strengthened partnerships with local organisations, enhancing the project's mission to promote science education and public engagement.
- **High Engagement and Attendance:** As a result of the awareness campaign, over **11500** people attended build-up activities and **5800** participated in the main event main event all across Portugal.

This consortium's approach to the biennium (2024-2025) reflects a commitment to making science accessible, inclusive, and engaging. By leveraging various communication channels and strategic partnerships, the project successfully achieved its primary objectives and contributed to the EU's goals of increasing public awareness and understanding of research and innovation. Looking ahead, the insights gained from this year's event will inform future editions of the European Researchers' Night, further improving the experience for participants and expanding the event's impact nationwide.

2. | Process and Objectives

The ERN's event was designed to align with the European Union's goals for science outreach, with focus on accessibility, inclusivity, and interactivity. To ensure that ERN's objectives meet EU's goals, the ERN communication plan was designed to promote build-up activities and events and coordinate the communication flow across all 9 venues. We followed a structured process composed of two main components: strategic planning and communication strategy implementation.

2.1 | Strategic planning

Initially, we outlined key objectives for the awareness campaign, aligning them with both the goals of the ERN project and the EU's vision for the ERN initiative. We aimed to:

- Increase the visibility of the event;
- Raise awareness for the day of the event, sparking curiosity for the activities scheduled to take place;
- Encourage the participation of different audiences, of all ages and socioeconomic backgrounds, in build-up activities and the main event;
- Convey complex scientific concepts in attractive and simple formats, so that a comfortable and inclusive environment is created for the community to learn;
- Show what the everyday life of a scientist looks like, deconstructing the idea typically associated with the profession;
- Highlight the practical importance of research and science in solving day-to-day problems;
- Spark audiences' critical thinking skills, encouraging them to explore and question their surroundings;
- Foster an interest in science and in pursuing a scientific career.

Aligned with our objectives, we then identified core target audiences, including students, schools, preschool-aged children, families and the general adult population. Additionally, we targeted researchers, their associated institutions, traditional media outlets, and community. Collaboration with these groups was essential as it enabled us to broaden our reach and expand the diversity of the activities offered.

2.2 | Communication strategy implementation

Based on our target audiences, we chose a multi-channel approach to maximise engagement. Channels included the ERN website, social media, newsletters, press releases, media partners and offline promotional materials. Each channel played a distinct role in effectively reaching specific audience segments.

ERN Website

The ERN website served as a database and repository of information about all aspects of the project (build-up activities, ERN, researchers at schools, venues, press, contacts and EU Corner),

where people could visit and find more information about our initiatives. Based on the issues detected in 2024, the website (<https://nei.cienciaviva.pt/2024-2025/>) has undergone changes that have improved navigation and clarity of the information available. During ERN 2025, some issues were detected regarding Search Engine Optimization (SEO), which we will explore further in this report.

Social Media

- Instagram: www.instagram.com/noitedosinvestigadores/
- Facebook: www.facebook.com/neinvestigadores
- X: https://x.com/NEI_pt
- TikTok: www.tiktok.com/@noiteinvestigadores
- YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/@noitedosinvestigadores8383>

Social media were mainly used to spark interest and get people talking about ERN, with the main goal of attracting visitors for the build-up activities and main events happening across all 9 venues. Overall, the channels were regularly updated with content throughout the year, designed to be accessible and engaging, emphasising the importance of science and research in everyday life. We planned weekly publications across all social media platforms and prepared a diverse range of materials to guide partners and associate institutions on this implementation.

In 2025, additional efforts were made to make digital communication more collaborative. We've decided to create a shared social media calendar, where the partners of the consortium could pitch their ideas and coordinate publications. To increase proximity to the audiences, we decided to invest more efforts in video content production, featuring researchers that would participate in the event in different locations, as well as other local public figures, briefly explaining what to expect and inviting people to attend ERN.

The remaining channels were promoted both at a national and regional level to leverage regional partnerships and protocols established by each venue.

By following this structured process and aligning each step with our primary objectives, the 2025 project successfully engaged a wide range of audiences, inspired curiosity, and promoted a positive view of science and research across Portugal as well as of EU research funding programmes.

3. | Communication channels and strategies

3.1 | Brand image

The ERN visual identity was consistently applied across all communication platforms throughout the project. In 2025, ERN's visual identity was maintained, following the revamp from the previous year, inspired by the previous project image (2021 edition).

To ensure that ERN's visual identity was consistently upheld across all venues and partners, we updated the existing visual identity manual (Figure 1) and communication toolkit, which included the logos and templates for different materials (offline promotion, social media and documents). The changes were mainly done to reflect the current year (2025) and ERN's date (Figure 2).

This manual was further supported by a general communication guidelines document (Figure 3), which included essential elements such as the financial statement, designated hashtags, ERN social media accounts to mention when sharing content on partners' platforms, and tailored recommendations for post types best suited to each communication channel.

Fig.1 Pages from the visual identity manual

Fig.2 2025 ERN's logo

Fig.3 Pages from the general communication guidelines manual

3.2 | Overview of channels used

The multi-channel approach employed by the ERN project was designed to reach a diverse audience across Portugal, leveraging multiple communication platforms such as:

ERN website

The website is a crucial tool to communicate, promote and organise project activities and serves as the project's central information hub. Just like in 2024, the website remained lodged in Ciência Viva's server, given its capacity to manage several websites at once and a dedicated IT team to match incoming demands, allowing us to save time and costs.

In 2025, the website suffered changes to improve clarity and navigation, while maintaining its simple and straightforward structure. Here are some of those changes:

- The **homepage** features a visually appealing banner with the logo, event date, venues and a promotional video. One block for build-up activities and another for Researchers at Schools activities were added to the homepage to make it easier to access.
- The **Navigation Bar** was reorganized (Figure 4):
 - We added a dropdown menu titled **"The Project"** ("O Projeto"), containing the "About" ("Sobre"), "Consortium" ("Consórcio") and "Past Editions" (Edições Anteriores").
 - The **About** page ("Sobre") contains a brief description of the event's history, objectives, and mission. The **Consortium page** ("Consórcio") contains information about the consortium institutions. The **Past Editions** page ("Edições Anteriores") contains the website for the consortium's last edition of ERN, in 2021.
 - We removed the Education dropdown menu ("Educação") and changed it into a single page called **Educational Activities** ("Atividades Educativas"). This page contains all the programmes under the "Researchers at schools" (WP3) activities: Meet the Scientist, Participatory Debates, Programme for Social Inclusion through Science, and Youth Ambassadors Program.
 - The **Activities for the Public** page ("Atividades para o Público") was added, to make the build-up activities easier to access by the public.
 - The **Resources** page ("Recursos") was added, with a collection of resources for teachers and students.
 - Additionally, there is a **Contact Us** page ("Contacte-nos") that presents visitors with the opportunity to contact the organisation, as well as with a Call to Action (CTA) to follow our social media accounts.
 - The **Venues** ("Locais"), **EU Corner**, **Press** ("Imprensa") and **Contacts** ("Contactos") pages remained the same as last year.

Fig.4 New website menu structure

Social Networks

Social media platforms like Instagram, X (formerly Twitter), YouTube, and TikTok are key tools for science communication due to their wide reach and ease of sharing information. Given their role as major information channels, they are essential for promoting ERN activities while also combating misinformation by ensuring accuracy. Each platform features tailored posts, with some common themes and formats across channels.

As we had more time between ERN 2024 and ERN 2025 compared to the period between the beginning of the project and ERN 2024, we were able to leverage our social media channels with a series of new post formats. One of our top priorities was also to commit to a collaborative strategy. We regularly created joint posts to expand reach and frequently engaged and collaborated with all partners' institutional channels, to leverage each other's unique capabilities. This approach allowed us to reach diverse demographics and adapt our messaging to maximise engagement.

Instagram

For ERN 2025, similarly to the previous year, our Instagram account (@noitedosinvestigadores), played a crucial role in connecting with our audience and promoting the ERN events. The platform allowed us to use a dynamic mix of posts, stories, and reels, showcasing both informative and interactive content tailored to foster curiosity and excitement about science. In 2025, we have initiated a new series of posts, namely:

1. **This week in news:** These posts aimed to share the latest news related to EU Missions and ERN, also visually represented by hashtags, such as #climatechange, #health, #ocean fostering interest and awareness. (Figure 5). Occasionally, we have also shared 'special editions' of this series, some of which featured the latest updates of ERN's team (Figure 6) and others which highlighted special events or celebrations such as 'International day of the Forests' and World's Glacier Day', (Figure 7).

Fig.5 Feed images representative of the series 'This week in news'.

Figure 6 - Feed image representative of a 'special edition' of the 'This week in news' series, featuring the update: 'ERN's EU-Embraces consortium got together in Porto to plan the next steps';

Figure 7 – Feed image representative of a ‘special edition’ of the ‘This week in news’ series, highlighting the international Forest Day and World’s Glaciers Day.

2. World Day Posts: This series aimed to raise awareness to World Day’s topics related to EU’s missions and further inform our audience about pressing issues such as right to education, gender equity in science, clean energy, access to water and many others, using the dates related to each one as an opportunity to delve further into these subjects. (Figure 8)

Figure 8 – Feed images representative of the series ‘World Day’, in this case ‘World Day to Combat Desertification and Drought’, celebrated on June 17th. The second and third slides convey further information about this topic.

3. Listen, Read and Watch: Seeking to build momentum to the big event, we’ve developed a series of posts suggesting materials to read (books and publications), listen (podcasts and radio shows) and watch (documentaries, movies, etc). These materials were in accordance with the 5 EU missions. We intended to motivate the audience to learn more about such topics, while promoting authors and agents actively looking to tackle these pressing issues. (Figure 9)

Figure 9 – Feed images representative of the series 'Listen, read and watch', in this case 'Listen, read and watch about the oceans'.

4. If you are attending ERN 2025 in...: To promote the nine cities where ERN 2025 took place, we created a series of posts suggesting relevant places to visit. This was intended to attract even more families and groups to participate, by turning their experience into a weekend trip filled with science, nature and culture. These posts always featured a final “Call to Action”, signalling each venue on a map, the date of the event and the exact location/address. (Figure 10)

Figure 10- Feed images representative of the series 'If you're attending ERN 2025 in...', in this case 'If you're attending ERN in Vila Nova de Foz Côa', highlighting some of the main attractions in the surrounding area.

5. A message from...: Following the aforementioned intention of increasing collaboration between partners and the wish to communicate more directly and engagingly with the audience, we produced a series of reels featuring both public figures and mediatic figures in the three biggest locations (Porto, Lisbon and Oeiras), and scientists that would be present in the main event. The main goal was to invite the public to attend by explaining ERN’s history and the democratization of scientific knowledge, emphasizing its interactive and informal format, and introducing scientists who explained what they do and what people could expect from the event. This series of reels proved to be very successful in terms of engagement and interaction, confirming its importance to our communication strategy. Furthermore, it contributed greatly to expand our audience, as we will expand further in this report. (Figure 11).

Figure 11 – Thumbnails from the reels part of the series ‘A message from...’, featuring from left to right: researcher Sílvia Conde from NOVA Medical School, Isaltino Morais, Oeiras’ city mayor, researcher Carla Oliveira from I3S, Eryl, ITQB NOVA’s mascot and researcher José Matos from INIAV.

For ERN 2025, we’ve also maintained and refined some of the previous year strategies’, namely:

1. Promoting activities posts: Similarly to last year, a large part of the content strategy centred on promoting upcoming build-up activities and sharing post-event recaps. Every pre-event was announced via Instagram Stories following a standardized layout that included essential details such as the date, time, venue (with location information), event title, and, when relevant, a link for further details or registration. These stories were organized into a dedicated highlight on the profile, ensuring easy access for all viewers (Figure 12). After each pre-event and inclusion for science activities, recap photos provided by the hosting venues were reshared on the ERN account, either through Instagram Stories or as part of the “That’s How It Happened” (“Foi Assim que Aconteceu”) post series (Figure 13). In 2025 we have also decided to test a new format for broader recaps like ‘Summer in pictures’ (Figure 13) or ERN’s event recap following current visual trends for carousel posts, which proved to be quite successful as a format.

Figure 13 – Example of the “That’s how it happened” posts.

2. Trending topics posts: We considered it essential for ERN's page to occasionally feature trending online topics to keep the content fresh, dynamic, and engaging. In the last trimester of 2024, we put this idea into practice with two themed posts. The first, published at the end of October, tapped into the widespread Halloween buzz, when many pages were releasing related content. We used the opportunity to discuss fear as a biological reaction, aligning with our mission to communicate science in an accessible and entertaining way, while connecting it to a theme naturally linked to the season. Similarly, in December, as social media was filled with users sharing their "Spotify Wrapped" summaries, we created ERN's own "Wrapped" post – a playful adaptation that highlighted the event and celebrated key achievements, effectively combining popular culture with our outreach goals.

More recently, following Dame Jane Goodall's passing, we have decided to create a tribute post that aimed to highlight her achievements, contribution to science and less known aspects of her environmental activism (Figure 14). Not only because of her prominent figure but also because her dedication to environmental preservation was closely related to the EU-Missions, particularly 'Adaptation to climate change'.

Figure 14 – Example of a Trending topic post, featuring Jane Goodall.

3. Program Highlights: We showcased the event lineup through carousel posts (Figure 15). Each slide highlighted the different activities happening at different venues, giving followers a preview of what they could look forward to at their local event.

Figure 15 – Example of a program highlight.

4. Event countdown videos: Similarly to 2024, in the weeks leading up to the main ERN event, we released a series of countdown videos designed to spark excitement and keep followers aware of ERN. The campaign kicked off with a “Two months until ERN” video that blended event promotion with informative content (Figure 16). A month before the big day, we posted an Instagram reel/stop-motion featuring photos taken at different spots at the three partner’s cities, inviting our audience to know both the event and each city (Figure 17).

Figure 16 – Frames from the 2 months to ERN countdown reel.

Figure 17 – Frames from the 1 month to ERN countdown reel.

On the last few days before the event, we’ve recorded several ‘behind the scenes’ moments in the three main venues of ERN and compiled them in a final countdown/ invitation in reel format on the day before ERN, attempting to show all the invisible work that an event of this size entails, in a dynamic and appealing way (Figure 18).

Figure 18 – Frames from the ‘Behind the scenes’ reel published on the day before the event.

5. Posts in collaboration: Following last year’s successful partnership we again joined Agenda Cultural do Porto to produce a promotional video designed to boost visibility for the upcoming ERN event in Porto (Figure 19). The video showcased the key features of the ERN initiative and

encouraged viewers to attend the event in Porto and other participating locations. It was published across both our channels and those of *Agenda Cultural do Porto* (with an audience of **86,500** followers), effectively broadening our outreach through their established community.

6. Interactive content: To foster dynamic and educational engagement, we leveraged

Figure 19 – Stills from the reel published in collaboration with Agenda Cultural do Porto.

Instagram Stories to develop interactive quizzes about the 5 EU Missions. Designed to both inform and entertain, these quizzes encouraged followers to challenge their knowledge on scientific and environmental topics. The series included two “Do You Know?” quizzes, two “Fact or Myth” editions, and one “Who Is Who” quiz (Figure 20).

Figure 20 – Example of ‘Do you Know or Not’ stories. This specific series of stories tried to inform our audiences about important parts of the event in a gamified and fun way.

7. Recap Videos and Photography Posts: Following the main event, we produced and shared both a ‘Best of’ photographic post and recap reel to remember some of the most memorable moments from ERN 25 (Figure 21 and 22). This content attempted to summarise and highlight the event, engage with the audience, and showcase the diverse range of activities held across various venues.

Figure 21 – Photo coverage of the event published by IQTB-NOVA, ERN and i3S, respectively.

Figure 22 – Reel recap of the event featuring clips and images from different venues of ERN 2025.

Overall, the ERN Instagram account has successfully refreshed its identity and prioritized the creation of content that is both informative and engaging. Through a balanced combination of promotional posts, interactive stories, and cohesive branding, the platform effectively built anticipation for the 2025 event while keeping followers consistently interested in science-related topics.

Facebook

Although our ERN's Facebook page continued to hold a solid follower base, engagement levels on this platform were noticeably lower compared to Instagram. This pattern reflects the general decline in user interaction observed on Facebook in recent years, particularly among younger audiences who tend to prefer more dynamic platforms such as Instagram and TikTok.

Taking this into account and aiming to maintain an active presence without allocating disproportionate resources to Facebook-specific content creation, we implemented a synchronised content strategy. All Instagram stories were automatically shared as Facebook stories, allowing the same interactive, educational, and promotional materials to be published simultaneously across both platforms with minimal additional effort.

When it came to Facebook posts, we primarily repurposed content originally developed for Instagram. The materials were adjusted to better match Facebook's visual format and user expectations. We also leveraged Facebook's capability to include hyperlinks directly in post descriptions, providing easy access to our website, YouTube channel, and other relevant resources.

Following ERN's event, we published dedicated photo albums for each venue, offering followers an engaging overview of the diverse activities, demonstrations, and audience participation that took place (Figure 23). These albums not only served as a visual archive of the event but also encouraged users to explore and interact with the extensive visual content at their own pace.

Figure 23 - Album covers and preview of the photo albums covering ERN 2025 at the three main venues (i3S, Pavilhão do Conhecimento and Marina de Oeiras).

Despite the general downward trend in Facebook engagement, our 2025 campaign achieved encouraging results. The synchronised approach proved effective in maintaining audience interest, increasing reach, and reinforcing ERN's visibility across all platforms.

X (formerly twitter)

On X, our main goal was to grow our presence, considering this platform is the one with the smallest following. To do so, we aimed to leverage the platform's real-time communication capabilities to promote ERN, share updates and engage with our audiences, using concise and engaging content. Our content primarily included:

- a) Event Announcements: Information about ERN 2025, emphasizing its role in bringing science closer to the public.

b) Promoting Interactive Build-up activities: Activities like “journeys into the unknown world of the brain,” offering educational and engaging experiences.

c) Open Day Promotions: Highlighting fully online and free events for students and teachers, including workshops and lab visits.

d) European Engagement: Participation in events like Europe Day in Brussels, discussing EU research missions and celebrating milestones such as the 75th anniversary of the Schuman Declaration.

e) Reposting relevant content from partner institutions, seeking to amplify credible scientific content, connect followers with a broader research community, and highlight collaborations with institutions or events. It allowed us to share timely updates, celebrate achievements, and engage audiences without creating all content from scratch, making science more accessible and visible to the public.

This page mainly served as a platform to engage the public with science and research in Portugal, promoting events, activities, and initiatives linked to ERN 2025 (Figure 24).

Figure 24 - Examples of posts and reposts done on X, during 2025. Left to right: Post created by ERN on World Bicycle Day, presenting data about its use and benefits. Repost of CIFEDES' post about their participation at ERN Pavilhão do Conhecimento. Repost of Agenda Cultural do Porto's post advertising ERN in Porto.

YouTube

YouTube plays the role of visually documenting and archiving ERN video content. The platform allows us to showcase both past and current activities, making videos easily accessible to a wide audience and highlighting the continuity and impact of the project over time.

Our approach this year was built upon what was established in ERN 2024, with key strategies including:

- **Organized Playlists for Content Exploration:** By maintaining themed playlists, viewers can easily navigate ERN's activities across different years. This structured approach not only simplifies video discovery but also illustrates the ongoing evolution and growth of the project.
- **Event Video Production:** We shared the TV spot for the ERN 2025 edition, introducing the event, its main locations, objectives, themes, and activities (Figure 25).

Despite the challenges of reaching a broad audience, YouTube has remained an essential component of our communication strategy. It serves as a comprehensive video archive, capturing the achievements and ongoing development of ERN while reinforcing its continued impact year after year.

Figure 25 - Frames from the ERN's 2025 promotional video published on Youtube.

TikTok

In 2025, ERN's TikTok page focused on interactive, lighthearted, and short-form content tailored to the platform's style: Videos featured researchers presenting their work and inviting viewers to ERN 2025, special posts like a Halloween-themed video, and recaps of build-up activities, generated a mix of engaging, easily digestible content that helped increase visibility and audience engagement throughout the year (Figure 26). These insights will support a more strategic and consistent TikTok presence moving forward.

While developing a substantial follower base is a gradual process, our more recent activity established a promising groundwork for future expansion and demonstrated TikTok's potential as a valuable channel for engaging younger, digitally active audiences in upcoming editions.

Figure 26 - Frames from some of the most interactive posts mentioned, published on TikTok during 2025: Top to bottom: Halloween themed post 'Why do we feel fear'; 'Explain your research in 12 words or less'; 'Which activity do you want to do with a friend' on behalf of International Friendship Day celebrated on July 20th.

Media

While social media played a crucial role in reaching our audiences, traditional media were essential to extending our reach and ensuring visibility across different demographic groups. Our approach to media outreach involved strategic coordination at both the national and regional levels, allowing us to maximise the impact of our message through various outlets, including newspapers, television radio, and online platforms.

Similarly to ERN 2024, to support media partners and encourage coverage of the event, we created a press kit, where we repurposed the materials created in 2024 and adapted for 2025. The kit included:

- **Press releases**: To continue the collaborative spirit of our strategy, it was decided that each partner would prepare and distribute their own press releases, to enhance communication at a local level and, eventually, nationally at strategic locations. Each partner prepared and distributed a press release (Examples in Annex 1) to relevant media outlets, offering an engaging overview of ERN 2025, its objectives, and key activities.
- **Sponsor Kit**: We developed a sponsor kit (Annex 2) that was sent to potential sponsors and suppliers at both national and regional levels. This included information on sponsorship and support opportunities, detailing how sponsors could gain exposure across ERN's media channels and communication platforms.
- **Visual materials**: All relevant materials such as the event's branding materials, logos, and banners were sent to associate partners, venues, media and others to ensure consistency in media coverage. (Annex 3)

To maximise the impact of our media promotion, we implemented the following strategies:

- **Put ERN at main cultural agenda websites**: we submitted the event to some of the main cultural agenda websites for several venues. For example, Porto, Oeiras, Lagos and Alviela had build-up activities or main event submitted to Viral Agenda, an online agenda with half a million views monthly. In Porto, we also included it in Agenda Cultural do Porto and Agenda Porto, the latter from the Porto's Municipality. ITQB NOVA also submitted its main event to Pumpkin.pt and Cartaz Cultural de Lisboa.
- **Media partners**: One of our main objectives was to establish a partnership with a broadcaster to ensure that ERN gained high-level visibility through TV or radio channels. We were able to establish a partnership with RTP2, RTP3, public TV broadcasters, and Antena 1, public radio broadcaster, to run ads about the main event. During and after the night, we had TV and radio coverage from Antena 1, CMTV, Now and SIC. Although the places covered were Oeiras and Lisbon, the event was presented as happening across Portugal. This allowed us to reach millions of people.

Offline promotion

To effectively promote the ERN event offline, we implemented a range of strategies aimed at reaching diverse audiences and maximising visibility. These strategies were executed at a national level whenever possible, while also incorporating significant local efforts. To this end, a diverse range of materials were developed and shared across all venues (Figure 27). These materials included:

- Poster
- Roll Up

- Invites
- Postcard
- Program template

Figure 27 – Some of the materials developed for ERN 2025: Poster, Rollup, postcard, invitation, program template.

Additionally, all venues received, within the Communication Toolkit (Figure 28), brand identity guidelines, including logos, colours and typography, enabling them to develop materials tailored to their specific space and event, always in line with the visual identity manual.

Figure 28 – Communication toolkit, visual identity manual and other materials shared through a common drive every venue had access to.

Regional Communication Efforts

The promotion of the ERN event across various regions involved a comprehensive mix of digital, print and broadcast media strategies. Each venue tailored its communication efforts to effectively reach local audiences, while keeping the alignment with the overarching ERN brand identity. Below are the key communications approaches implemented by the different venues:

- **Social Media Campaigns**: All venues used platforms like Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, X, and YouTube to engage with their local communities. The social media campaigns included regular posts, event countdowns, and promotional videos that highlighted key aspects of the ERN event, driving traffic to event pages and increasing engagement. The collaboration between venues was crucial; when partners shared posts featuring the ERN identity to promote their events and programs, it significantly enhanced our collective visibility and reinforced a unified brand message, which helps clarify the consortia's involved venues and partners. By leveraging each venue's audience, we were able to amplify our communication efforts and create a more cohesive promotional narrative.
- **Newsletters and websites**: Newsletters allowed venues to directly inform their audience about upcoming activities and provide event updates. The official ERN website, as well as individual venue websites, were regularly updated with relevant information, ensuring easy access to event details.
- **Press Releases and Media Coverage**: Each partner has developed their own Press releases, tailored to their own main events, that were sent to both regional and national media outlets, securing coverage in newspapers, TV channels, and local news websites. Some venues achieved television exposure on channels like SIC, CMTV and Porto Canal as well as radio interviews on stations like Antena 1, broadening the event's reach.
- **Local partnerships and collaborations**: Collaborations with local municipalities, such as the Municipality of Oeiras, played a key role in promoting the event. These partnerships helped integrate ERN promotion into municipal websites, social media platforms, and local initiatives, such as street signage and community engagement efforts.
- **Outdoor advertising**: Several venues resorted to banners and outdoor screens to maximise visibility in public spaces. This offline promotion effectively complemented the digital campaigns and expanded the event's awareness to a broader audience.
- **Merchandising and printed materials**: Venues distributed flyers, posters and merchandise in local bars and restaurants. These materials ensured that the event remained visible and accessible to local communities.
- **Event listings and regional agendas**: As said before, many venues leveraged local event platforms and regional agendas, such as "Viral Agenda" or Pumpkin.pt, to list ERN and boost attendance. These listings provided an additional promotional layer that targeted audiences actively seeking events in the area.

Altogether, these regional communication efforts ensured that ERN reached a wide and diverse audience, effectively promoting both the event and the importance of science communication in local communities.

4. | Metrics and Evaluation

This section provides an overview of the metrics collected across multiple domains to assess the project's impact, identify success, and guide improvements for future editions. By monitoring

various indicators, we aimed to measure the effectiveness of our communication strategies, audience engagement, and media presence.

4.1 | Digital platforms Analytics

As previously discussed, digital platforms are a fundamental tool in the ERN communication strategy. To understand the effectiveness of our strategies, it is essential to analyse metrics from both the ERN website and social media channels. By analysing these metrics, we can gain valuable insights into user behaviour, content performance, and the reach of our messaging.

4.1.1 | Website

The analysis of the ERN 2025 website performance reveals crucial insights regarding user behaviour, engagement levels, and areas for improvement. The data that will be presented below is from the year 2025.

In general, the website, <https://nei.cienciaviva.pt/>, received around 18700 unique visitors and 96300, with a bounce rate of 41%. This could be explained by the number of visits for previous editions, such as the 2021 edition, that may have been looking for ERN 2025.

The landing page, <https://nei.cienciaviva.pt/2024-2025/>, received a substantial amount of traffic, recording 6900 visitors and 22400 pageviews. These values include several other landing page subdirectories that redirected to the landing page (</2024-2025/index.php>, </2024/>, </2024-2025/>, </2024/index.php>), which had their own data.

Nevertheless, these numbers are somewhat misleading, as this page serves as both the landing page and a collection point for other sections of the website. Therefore, it is challenging to ascertain user interactions with specific content elements, such as visits on the "Activities for the Public", "Press", "Contacts", and "Resources" sections and the list of venues, which is vital for understanding engagement levels. The bounce rate for this landing page stands at 42%, suggesting that while many visitors are entering the site, a significant portion is not engaging with the content presented. This indicates a potential need for improved navigation or introductions of content that visitors can engage and scroll down to explore further.

The About page, <https://nei.cienciaviva.pt/2024-2025/sobre>, had **221** visitors with a higher bounce rate of **67%**, indicating that visitors do not interact with the page and move on to other pages or leave the website. Similarly, the Partners page, <https://nei.cienciaviva.pt/2024-2025/parceiros>, recorded **99** visitors with a bounce rate of **82%**. This indicates that visitors do not find this page's content interesting and leave the page. This could be explained by the presence of external links on this page, which will make visitors leave. The decrease in the number of visitors, compared to 2024, may be due to the changes implement on the website, which hid these two pages on a drop-down list.

Nevertheless, it is important to optimise both pages, as they contain essential information about our mission, values, and partners that underpin our project. Engaging our audience with our objectives is crucial, especially given the existence of other consortia in Portugal.

The page "Educational Activities", implemented this year, received 409 visitors, 718 visits, and has a 32% bounce rate, which is a good value for the education and science sectors, according to the [Marketing Platform CXL](#). This indicates that this page was a good addition to the Navigation Bar.

Despite all the issues identified, the overall performance presents a strong foundation for future improvements. The substantial visitor numbers indicate a keen interest in the content and an effective outreach strategy. The commitment to ongoing improvement reflects our dedication to fostering a vibrant community around the ERN initiatives, ensuring that we can better serve our audience and fulfil our mission in the coming edition.

4.1.1.1. | Improvements for future editions

For future editions, we suggest the following actions to improve the overall user experience, make our website more intuitive and increase the number of visits:

- Change website domain: This was a point for improvement identified last year, but it was not possible to implement it. According to user behaviour, people rarely search for the event under its acronym (NEI – in portuguese) and, instead, they are more likely to search for “European Researchers’ Night” (“Noite Europeia dos Investigadores” in portuguese). Changing the domain to reflect the event’s full name (for example <https://noiteuropeiainvestigadores.cienciaviva.pt>), would increase the chances of appearing higher in search engine results and attracting relevant traffic to the website.
- Rank the website higher in search engines: This year, on search engines such as Google, our project page was difficult to locate, since it didn't appear in the first positions. To make the website appear higher, we suggest taking some actions to optimize it, such as optimize title tags, meta descriptions and keywords, use internal linking, add alt text to all images and optimize URL slugs, avoiding numbers or words that have no meaning or context within the project.
- Make event programmes easier to locate: Currently, to find the event programmes, visitors must go to each venues pages individually and click on the Programme button. It would make it easier to make them accessible in one place, such as the navigation bar on a dropdown menu, or embed it on each venues page, without the need to click on a button. This would make it easier for users to find the information they are seeking, decreasing confusing situations, and enhancing engagement.

4.1.2 | Social Media

Regarding the evaluation of social media analytics for the ERN 2025 project, we focused on performance metrics across our primary platforms: Instagram, Facebook, X, YouTube and TikTok. Each platform offers unique insights into audience engagement, allowing us to assess the impact of our communication strategies. Across all platforms, the data correspond to the period between October 11th 2024 and October 22nd 2025, which marked the end of ERN 2024 and the End of 2025's communication efforts, respectively.

Instagram Analytics

Instagram reached 34.800 accounts, (a growth of **226.1%** compared to the previous year) the vast majority being non-followers, aligning with ERN current followers' base of **1400**. The platform effectively attracted a broader audience beyond the existing followers, demonstrating that the content strategy broke out of ERN's immediate network and engaged a wider public, a key goal for increasing awareness and outreach.

During this period, the account saw a significant growth of **47.7%**, with an increase of **452** followers (rising from **948** to **1,400**). This impressive growth exceeded the follower target set for both editions (**1,000** followers). However, there's still potential to enhance follower conversion from the high volume of new viewers. Implementing stronger conversion tactics (such as using end-of-reel and story prompts to encourage follows or including more direct calls-to-action in captions) could help drive even greater follower gains.

Content varied between **77** posts, **427** stories and **29** reels, each format performing differently:

- Reels performed exceptionally well in terms of interactions, with around **1400** accounts

reacting, saving and commenting with the 29 reels published, demonstrating that this format is highly favoured by Instagram's algorithm and audience.

- Photo / Static posts attracted **203** interactions, illustrating that static images and carousels remain effective, though less so than video content.
- Stories were viewed by **64.200 accounts**, also garnered substantial reach, with **73.000** accounts reached.

Overall, we had **189.700** views on our content and **2700** accounts interacted with it, with a growth of **100%** compared to last year.

The top three pieces of content published by ERN's page, included 1 post (September 19th 2025) and 2 reels (December 17th 2024 and September 2nd 2025) in terms of reach.

- September 19th 2025 post (Figure 29): **18.800 views, 185 likes, 6 saves, 39 profile visits**. This post converted into **10** new followers. Dedicated to promoting ERN's detailed programme

Figure 29 - Post featuring ERN's general program.

across the different venues, the post attracted strong engagement not only from regular followers but also from new audiences, with **87.4%** of viewers being non-followers. This wide reach and interest likely contributed to raising awareness and encouraging attendance at the event, effectively supporting its overall promotion.

- December 17th 2024 reel (Figure 30): **13.100 views, 150 likes, 3 saves, 15 profile visits**. This reel converted into new followers. In this video, we asked several researchers to explain their research in 12 words or less. This reel performed particularly well because it combined several elements that resonate strongly on social media. The challenge format: asking researchers to explain their work in 12 words or less, created an engaging and playful dynamic that encouraged curiosity and participation. It also helped to humanize science by giving a

Figure 30 - Reel featuring several researchers explaining their work in 12 words or less.

face and voice to the researchers behind the work, allowing the audience to connect with them on a more personal level. Additionally, the informal tone and relaxed setting made the content feel authentic and approachable, standing out from more traditional, formal science communication and appealing to a broader audience.

- September 2nd 2025 reel (Figure 31): In the first reel of the series 'A message from...' we had one of the most successful reels, featuring Dr. Alexandre Quintanilha. ERN's Instagram page gained a total of **33** new followers. It was visualized by **8030** people, **77%** of which were non-followers of the page and had **330** interactions, the vast majority by non-followers (73.7%).

Figure 31 – Reel featuring academic Alexandre Quintanilha, part of the series 'A message from...'.

- It's worth highlighting that the most successful post featured in ERN's page, during this period, was a reel produced by ITQB Nova in collaboration with Oeiras' mayor, Isaltino Morais and his communication office (Figure 33). This underscores the value of working collaboratively, not only with the institutions that make up the consortium, but also with other key local stakeholders. Engaging public institutions and prominent local figures who play an active role in their communities can significantly strengthen ERN's reach and impact. This reel was viewed around **53.000 times**, generating **1659** interactions (**1561** likes, **31** comments and **67** shares).

Figure 33 – Reel published by Isaltino Morais in collaboration with ERN, featuring the mayor of Oeiras, part of the series 'A message from...'.

- September 30th 2025 post (Figure 34): **8635** views, **247** likes, **4** saves, **18** profile visits. This post converted into 1 new follower. It was created also in collaboration with one of the institutions of the consortium, i3S, which contributed to its success. The post portrayed European Researcher's Night 2025 at this venue and it proved highly successful, as it captured authentic moments and conveyed the atmosphere of the activities. By showcasing real participants and interactions, this type of content enhanced authenticity and encouraged higher engagement rates, as people featured in the photos and their networks were more likely to interact and share the content.

Facebook Analytics

Despite some challenges, Facebook continued to play an important role in ERN's communication strategy, serving as a reliable channel to reach and engage its audience. The data demonstrates the platform's effectiveness in sustaining outreach, particularly among older demographics and in maintaining overall visibility. Over the reporting period, the page reached approximately **12,000** accounts – an impressive **87.6% increase** compared to the previous year. Additionally, **3,300** profile visits were recorded, reflecting consistent interest in the ERN initiative. Interaction levels also rose considerably, up by **92%**, with a total of **1,035** interactions, including **891** reactions, **31** comments, and **113** post shares. Meanwhile, the follower base remained steady at around **5,100**, indicating a committed and loyal audience.

In terms of content performance, multi-image posts achieved the highest engagement, followed by stories and reels. The audience remained predominantly based in Portugal (**90.7%**), with the largest shares coming from Lisbon (**31.8%**) and Porto (**26.1%**). These results align with ERN's main areas of activity, though they also point to opportunities for expanding regional engagement in future campaigns.

These outcomes are consistent with realistic expectations and demonstrate solid progress. Moving forward, emphasis will be placed on multi-photo and interactive content, coupled with stronger calls-to-action, seeking to further enhance engagement and extend ERN's reach.

X Analytics

Currently, obtaining detailed analytics from X remains challenging, which limited our ability to conduct a comprehensive performance assessment. However, given the relatively small following of **100** users, it became clear that this platform was not a primary communication channel for ERN. Instead, it was strategically used to amplify content from more active partners through retweets and to occasionally share adapted versions of posts originally created for Facebook and Instagram. These included event recaps and posts celebrating international dates such as World Wildlife Day and World Water Day, in a total of **26** posts, ensuring a consistent yet proportionate presence on the platform.

YouTube Analytics

For ERN 2025, activity on YouTube was more limited than on other platforms, as we prioritised short-video content on other platforms. Consequently, only one video was published on the main ERN YouTube channel, as the Ad spot for TV was published on *Pavilhão do Conhecimento's* channel. These served as complementary materials to the website, where they attracted a significant share of the overall audience's views. Over the past year, ERN's Youtube channel has presented modest results, with **32** subscribers and **175** new views, **296** impressions and a relatively low click rate of **4.4%**, mainly on desktop environment, contrary to most of the content presented in other social media platforms. To improve this performance, it will be important, in possible future editions, to rethink CTAs and thumbnails, making them more engaging, concise and visually appealing, seeking to encourage more meaningful interactions with our audience.

The strong performance of short video content on other platforms, such as Instagram reels, combined with the widespread popularity of YouTube Shorts, suggests that experimenting with this format on YouTube could be highly beneficial. Introducing shorter, more dynamic videos may help boost both audience reach and view counts, particularly on mobile devices, where most YouTube users now consume content. This approach could therefore play an important role in expanding ERN's visibility and engagement on the platform.

TikTok Analytics

From October 2024 to October 2025 ERN's account reached a total of **5,700** users, including **5,600** new ones, and generated around **3,000** additional video views across the 11 videos published. While engagement metrics (**27** likes, **20** profile visits, and **3** shares) indicate room for growth, these results represent a solid foundation for future development. Given the strong performance achieved on Instagram, our focus this year naturally prioritized that platform. However, moving forward, a more diversified, multi-channel approach, coupled with more regular posting and the adoption of trending TikTok formats could further enhance reach and engagement across platforms.

Unlike the previous edition, this year we reached the younger audience that TikTok is best known for, achieving one of our key objectives for the platform. The majority of our viewers were aged **18–24 (44.8%)**, followed by **25–34 (36.8%)** and **35–44 (9.9%)**, confirming that the updated content strategy effectively attracted our intended demographic. The gender distribution was also well balanced, with male viewers representing **53%** and female viewers **47%**. This near parity demonstrates the platform's broad appeal across genders, which constitutes an encouraging sign for future content planning, allowing for inclusive communication without the need to focus on a single demographic segment.

To continue growing our audience in future editions, we intend to focus on increasing posting consistency and tailoring content to each platform's strengths. Experimenting with short, trend-based videos and behind-the-scenes clips could boost visibility among younger audiences. Collaborations with researchers, influencers, or partner institutions would help expand reach and credibility. Additionally, investing in paid promotion for key posts and optimizing hashtags and captions for discoverability can enhance engagement. Finally, maintaining a regular posting schedule and cross-promoting content across platforms will support steady audience growth and stronger brand recognition.

Overall, the 2025 social media campaign effectively achieved its main goals, significantly increasing awareness of both the ERN 2025 event and the EU-EMBRACES project and managing to translate these numbers into more participants at the actual event. Building on the experience and insights gained from the 2024 edition, this year's strategy reached new levels of performance by rethinking content formats and experimenting with fresh, more engaging approaches. Collaboration played a key role in this success: joint efforts among partner institutions, along with the participation of researchers and public figures, helped humanize the campaign and bring the event closer to its audience.

Through a combination of targeted posts, interactive formats, and tailored strategies for each platform, we reached close to 53,000 users, engaging a broad and diverse audience while strengthening ERN's online presence. Despite these positive outcomes, there remains room for growth, particularly on TikTok, which continues to be an essential platform for reaching younger audiences, and on YouTube, which holds great potential as a complementary channel for event promotion and visibility.

4.1.2.1. Considerations for future editions

- Expand and explore the potential of our collaborative strategy to include the less populated cities: This year, the European Researchers' Night (ERN) saw a remarkable improvement in collaboration across the consortium's venues and organizations, particularly among the three partners: i3S (Porto), *Pavilhão do Conhecimento - Centro de Ciência Viva* (Lisbon), and ITQB-NOVA (Oeiras). The stronger coordination between these centres allowed for a more cohesive program, better resource sharing, and an overall enhancement of participant engagement. Looking ahead, it will be essential to extend this collaborative spirit to less populated cities,

ensuring that the positive outcomes and visibility achieved in the main cities are equally distributed across the country. This can be accomplished by involving local agents, both researchers and community figures, and by building partnerships with strategic stakeholders such as town halls, schools, and cultural institutions. Strengthening local ownership through early engagement, regional ambassadors, and tailored communication strategies could further deepen impact.

- Increase our Tiktok presence, to attract younger audiences: It will be important to further study and develop tailored strategies for TikTok, as its dynamics differ significantly from platforms like Instagram. TikTok thrives on short, creative, and trend-driven videos that favour authenticity and spontaneity. This format is particularly effective for engaging younger audiences, especially teenagers, who respond better to informal and relatable storytelling. In this edition, we already saw promising results with videos of this kind, such as the one where researchers casually talked about their work, which generated strong engagement and positive feedback. Building on this success, future editions should invest in a more structured TikTok strategy, including trend-based content, researcher challenges, and behind-the-scenes moments, to deepen our connection with this key audience segment.
- Adapt to trends and current events and conversations: Adapting to social media trends, current events, and ongoing conversations is essential to keeping our communication fresh, relevant, and engaging. This year, we already saw positive results with this strategy, which we recommend reinforcing in future editions. By aligning our content with what audiences are already discussing or experiencing online, we can increase visibility and foster a stronger emotional connection with the public. However, it is equally important to ensure that these efforts remain anchored in our core mission of promoting the European Researchers' Night and raising awareness of science, research, and innovation. Balancing trend-based creativity with consistent messaging allows us to stay culturally in tune while continuing to highlight the value of scientific work and its impact on society.

4.2 | Media Coverage

As aforementioned, media outlets were essential for the ERN 2025 strategy to broaden and ensure that the event reached a wide audience. The project gained significant traction across both national and regional outlets, with a total of 30 articles, reports and broadcasts referencing ERN 2025 (Annex 4). This is a testament to the widespread interest from various media channels. Table 1 summarises clipping data.

- At a national level, 9 articles were published, ensuring broad visibility across Portugal. These national outlets played a crucial role in bringing ERN 2025 to the attention of the general public, particularly in urban centres and among those with a strong interest in science and research.

Table 1 - Article numbers by venue

Venue	Number of articles
CCV Alviela	5
CCV Estremoz	—
CCV Braga	—
CCV Bragança	—

Venue	Number of articles
CCV Lagos	3
i3S	5
Museu do Côa	—
Pavilhão do Conhecimento	2
Oeiras – ITQB NOVA	6

At a regional level, several venues successfully garnered significant media attention. This reflects not only a strong local interest but also effective communication and promotion efforts.

Certain venues, such as CCV Estremoz, CCV Braga, CCV Bragança and Museu do Côa, did not achieve any mentionable media coverage, as indicated by the lack of articles in the data. This underscores potential areas for improvement in engaging local media for future editions.

Two of the national articles referring to ERN 2025 were published in *Público* on September 26. One provided an in-depth description of all venues and their activities and other was an opinion article of the three partners' coordinators on the importance of celebrating science. These articles, featured in such a significant newspaper which averages more than **54000** paid subscriptions per month, gave ERN substantial visibility across the country and served as invaluable promotion for the project.

Also, during the main event, we got live coverage from one public radio national broadcaster – Antena 1, which enabled people to be aware about the event as it was happening. According to RTP, Antena 1 had, on average, **497000** listeners per day during the first semester of 2025. Although we do not have data on how many listeners the live coverage got, these numbers can reflect how we were able to reach a larger audience across Portugal.

On the days following ERN, the main events were covered on three TV National Broadcasters – CMTV, Now and SIC. Although these television reports were after ERN, these serve as important means of publicizing the event to a wider community, which will then be more attentive to future editions.

TV and Radio Ads

We ran ads on 2 Public TV channels (RTP2 and RTP3) and one public radio broadcaster (Antena 1), repeated 21 times in each, over the course of 7 days (September 19th to September 25th) on different periods of the day. The data is available on Annex 5.

It is challenging to determine an exact number of viewers and listeners reached through our TV and radio advertisements, as the broadcasting stations do not provide detailed audience data. This lack of access to viewership and listenership metrics makes it difficult to measure the precise impact of our campaigns.

Additionally, since the ads were aired at various times throughout the day, from late-night slots to prime time, the potential audience size varied significantly. Viewership and listenership numbers fluctuate considerably depending on the schedule, further complicating efforts to establish an accurate overall estimate of our reach.

The estimate of total TV viewership is **3.000.000** people on prime time (8-12PM in Portugal) and 2.000.000 in the afternoons, with no further data for the remaining hours. RTP2 has around **0.9%** sharing of prime time and afternoons which allows us to estimate that our spot reached at least around **279.000** people during the times it was played within these timeframes on this channel (12 of the 21 times).

There are no public data concerning RTP3 and Antena 1's viewership which prevents us for knowing how many people were reached through these campaigns.

As a whole, the media coverage achieved through media outlets, combined with targeted advertising efforts, contributed to build anticipation and excitement for the ERN event and promote the EU-Embraces project.

4.3 | Regional campaigns

Each venue used a mix of digital and physical promotional strategies, including social media posts, email newsletters, local advertisements, and partnerships. Venues aimed to raise awareness of ERN's events and attract participants from various demographic groups, from students to local families and professionals.

Similarly to last year ITQB NOVA, in partnership with Câmara Municipal de Oeiras, positioned outdoors and Mupis across the city. The four physical outdoors were exposed from September 15th to September 28th in high-traffic areas such as Oeiras Forum, Porto Salvo and Laje. A physical outdoor was on display from September 10th to September 16th, on Oeiras Parque, another high-traffic area of the city. In addition, ITQB NOVA promoted ERN with a banner on Corrida do Tejo, a 10 Km run in Oeiras, reaching **8000** people. In Porto, i3S promoted the event through various communication channels offered by the University of Porto (UP), including UP News, and the university's Facebook. On average, UP News reaches **50000** page views per month. UP's Facebook page has approximately **180000** followers. i3S also distributed **300** flyers to local business and Faculties of the University of Porto. Furthermore, the event was featured in the Ciência et al newsletter (i3S's educational outreach program), reaching an audience of **398** teachers, and i3S' internal newsletter, with around **1000** followers.

Many of the regional communication efforts are challenging to quantify in metrics. However, it's important to acknowledge the social media presence across the nine venues associated with this consortium. Below is the follower count for each venue on Instagram:

CCV Alviela: 1563
 CCV Braga: 2518
 CCV Bragança: 1646
 CCV Estremoz: 1258
 ITQB NOVA: 3308
 i3S: 5291
 CCV Lagos: 1950
 Museu do Côa: 6549
 Pavilhão do Conhecimento: 23700

These follower bases play a crucial role in enhancing ERN's visibility, significantly expanding outreach and engagement at the local level. Below, we present the metrics for selected Instagram posts shared by our partners, which illustrate the engagement and reach achieved through their collaborative support. To ensure consistency across the selected posts, we focused on the metrics for posts that showcased each venue's program, a format utilised by all venues:

Pavilhão do Conhecimento shared a post on September 25 (Figure 35), reaching a total of **57** interactions (**38** likes, **1** repost, **18** shares).

Figure 35 - Post published by Pavilhão do Conhecimento preceding the event.

i3S shared a post on September 24 (Figure 36), reaching a total of **3434** accounts and **9874** views. Out of these, 92 accounts engaged with the content, with a total of **131** interactions (**75** likes, **6** saves, **40** shares and **10** external link taps).

Figure 36 - Post published by i3S preceding the event.

ITQB NOVA shared a post on September 25 (Figure 37), reaching a total of **84** interactions (**56** likes, **1** repost, **26** shares).

Figure 36 - Post published by i3S preceding the event.

CCV Bragança shared a post on September 22 (Figure 38), reaching a total of **19** interactions (**17** likes, **1** repost, **7** shares).

Figure 38 - Post published by CCV Bragança preceding the event.

CCV Braga shared a post on September 24 (Figure 39), reaching a total of **25** interactions (**20** likes, **1** repost, **4** shares).

Figure 39 - Post published by CCV Braga preceding the event.

CCV Alviela shared a post on September 19 (Figure 40), reaching a total of **17** interactions (**14** likes, **1** comment, **1** repost, **1** shares).

Figure 40 - Post published by CCV Alviela preceding the event.

4.4 | Attendance and Reach

The reach and attendance metrics provide a crucial measure of the overall success of the ERN 2025 awareness campaign. Build-up activities served as key promotional tools and engagement boosters leading up to the main event, allowing us to create early momentum and build interest across different audience segments. Understanding how these communication efforts translated into attendance—both in the build-up activities and the main event—helps us assess the effectiveness of our strategy in reaching and engaging target groups. Table 2 summarises this data.

Table 2 - Number of participants in build-up activities and main event.

Venue	Build-up activities	Participants Build-up activities	Participants Main Event
CCV Alviela	Activity 1	10	50
	Activity 2	30	
	Activity 3	22	
CCV Estremoz	Activity 1	490	270
	Activity 2	42	
	Activity 3	50	
CCV Braga	Activity 1	35	68
	Activity 2	30	
	Activity 3	160	
CCV Bragança	Activity 1	31	280
	Activity 2	28	
	Activity 3	15	
CCV Lagos	Activity 1	53	68
	Activity 2	25	
	Activity 3	120	
	Activity 4	41	
i3S	Activity 1	50	1000
	Activity 2	200	
	Activity 3	4	
	Activity 4	14	
	Activity 5	6	

Venue	Build-up activities	Participants Build-up activities	Participants Main Event
Museu do Côa	Activity 1	25	1000
	Activity 2	30	
	Activity 3	11	
Pavilhão do Conhecimento	Activity 1	2700	1900
	Activity 2	20	
	Activity 3	4000	
ITQB-NOVA	Activity 1	14	2000
	Activity 2	2000	
	Activity 3	1200	
	Activity 4	60	

During build-up activities, the total number of people reached across all venues exceeded **11500**. These numbers are highly positive, highlighting the importance of build-up activities both as a means of promoting the European Researchers' Night (ERN) and bringing science to a broad range of communities throughout the country. Furthermore, the success of the build-up activities suggests that early communication efforts, through media campaigns and community partnerships, effectively built anticipation for both the build-up activities and the main event.

The varying levels of attendance reflect the diverse nature of the participating venues and their respective audiences. Communication strategies were therefore adapted to each context: larger venues were able to benefit from more extensive social media and media outreach, while smaller venues required a more localised approach.

As a result of these outcomes and the wider efforts of the Awareness Campaign, participation in the main event in 2025 was equal to or significantly higher than that of ERN 2024, with a total of **5800** participants. This increase in attendance was observed at almost all venues, except for CCV Braga and Museu do Côa, where participation decreased. In the case of CCV Braga, this reduction can be explained by the fact that another consortium held its own ERN event in the same city, splitting the audience's attention between the two. At the Museu do Côa, the lower turnout is likely due to its remote location. For future editions, it will be important to strengthen regional promotion in this area and broaden outreach efforts to attract participants from other regions.

When analysing attendance and reach data, it is important to consider the specific contexts of each venue – particularly their size and geographical location. Venues based in major urban areas, such as *Pavilhão do Conhecimento* in Lisbon, *Marina de Oeiras* in Oeiras, or *i3S* in Porto, naturally attracted larger numbers of participants during both the build-up activities and the main event. This reflects not only the higher population density in these areas but also the strong reputation and visibility of these institutions.

In contrast, venues located in smaller regions – such as CCV Alviela or CCV Lagos – understandably recorded lower attendance figures. However, considering their local populations and regional reach, these numbers still represent successful community engagement. CCV Alviela managed to maintain its previous level of participation, while CCV Lagos achieved an increase. The communication strategy in these areas focused on local partnerships and community involvement, proving effective within the constraints of their smaller populations.

In summary, both national and regional dissemination efforts were highly successful, leading to a substantial increase in participation during the main event and building momentum for future editions. While attendance was naturally higher in more populated areas, communication strategies were effective in maximising reach relative to the scale of each venue's community. By tailoring the approach to regional contexts and leveraging both national and local communication channels, the ERN project successfully engaged a wide and diverse audience across Portugal. This underscores the importance of adapting communication strategies to the size and characteristics of each venue to ensure the fullest possible audience engagement.

5. | Conclusion

The ERN 2025 awareness campaign achieved significant strides in reaching and engaging diverse audiences. Compared to the 2024 edition, we had an **increase of 18.4%** in overall visitors, with a global number of **5800** participants across the country. These numbers reflected a growth in the amount of visitors in practically all venues, with the exception of Braga and Vila Nova de Foz Côa. These locations each presented a different set of challenges that might help explain this phenomenon: in Braga, there were two ERN's happening simultaneously, organized by two different consortiums, which likely contributed to fewer attendees as the target audience was the same. On the other hand, the geographical location of Vila Nova de Foz Côa may help explain the lower number of visitors during this year's European Researchers' Night. As a smaller and more remote area, it naturally faces challenges in attracting large audiences. Limited public transportation options and the distance from larger cities can make it more difficult for visitors to attend in person. Despite these factors, maintaining ERN activities in such regions remains crucial to ensuring inclusivity and promoting science beyond metropolitan areas, helping to gradually build stronger local engagement over time.

Every component of the communication campaign contributed in its own way to enhancing visibility, encouraging participation, and strengthening the connection between the public and the mission of the European Researchers' Night.

The performance on social media platforms like Instagram and TikTok was instrumental in reaching a diverse range of audiences. Instagram, as our most engaged platform, successfully attracted a broad audience through a mix of posts, stories and reels, achieving noteworthy metrics in audience reach and engagement. Similarly, TikTok allowed us to explore a younger demographic with visually engaging, promotional content, while X provided an accessible, structured feed for updates and quick interactions. While Facebook's engagement was modest, it reinforced the need to leverage cross-platform synergies and evaluate platform-specific strategies moving forward. YouTube also presented both opportunities and limitations: the positive results achieved with short-form video content on platforms like Instagram Reels highlight a valuable opportunity for future campaigns on Youtube, namely investing in the Youtube Shorts' format. Incorporating this format into ERN's YouTube strategy could significantly enhance visibility and engagement, especially among mobile users who represent the majority of the platform's audience.

Our website served as a central information hub, attracting thousands of visits and providing valuable insights into user behaviour. The implementations made since last year, particularly in the UX / UI realm, have already helped enhance navigation and overall usability, making it easier for visitors to access relevant information. Looking ahead, investing in SEO strategies will also be essential to increase the website's visibility, helping it appear at the top of major search engines and making information about the European Researchers' Night even more accessible to the public.

The media and regional awareness initiatives for ERN 2025 played a pivotal role in expanding visibility and strengthening engagement across a wide range of communities. By fostering strategic collaborations with national media outlets and implementing locally focused campaigns, we effectively adapted our communication to regional contexts while maintaining a cohesive ERN identity. National exposure was boosted through targeted advertising, press coverage, and key partnerships that ensured a strong presence in both traditional and digital media. At the same time, the efforts of our partner venues at the regional level deepened community involvement by promoting ERN activities through locally relevant platforms and audiences, creating a balanced and far-reaching communication strategy.

The multi-channel strategy implemented for ERN 2025 effectively broadened our reach and improved access to event information across diverse platforms. By continuously refining our communication efforts and incorporating feedback from participants and partners, we are confident in the ability to further strengthen visibility, engagement, and the overall event experience in future editions. The lessons and insights gained from this year's campaign provide a solid foundation for building an even more impactful approach, one that deepens ERN's connection with its audiences, fosters curiosity, and continues to inspire public interest in science and research.

ANNEX

European Researchers' Night 2024/25

Communication Report

D6.1. Awareness Campaign 2025

1 | Press Release

Example of a Press Release

Luísa Melo
 Unidade de Comunicação i3S
 Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde
 Rua Alfredo Allen, 208 | 4200-135 Porto
 Tlm: 917 585 435
 e-mail: lmelo@i3s.up.pt

COMUNICADO DE IMPRENSA

Noite Europeia dos Investigadores: Ciência para todos no Porto

Explorar o cosmos e conhecer a «Constelação do Dragão», resolver enigmas e decifrar códigos para controlar uma infeção desconhecida, descobrir como os arqueólogos reconstróem o passado, participar numa sessão noturna de observação de insetos, descobrir como o corpo humano pode ser a energia do futuro e como a ciência e a engenharia podem unir-se para salvar vidas são apenas algumas das atividades da Noite Europeia dos Investigadores que, no Porto, se realizam no **Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde da Universidade do Porto (i3S) a 26 de setembro**. E isto é só uma amostra de uma vasta programação que promete surpreender e envolver o público em experiências imersivas de ciência e tecnologia. Está pronto para aceitar o desafio e entrar no fascinante mundo da investigação científica?

A Noite Europeia dos Investigadores (NEI) chega ao Porto com uma festa que visa aproximar cientistas e a sociedade civil oferecendo cerca de 50 atividades experimentais e lúdicas para públicos de todas as idades. Entre as 18 e as 23 horas, e desta vez tendo como parceiro «fora da caixa» o Museu do FCPorto, mais de 150 investigadores vão mobilizar-se para partilhar a sua paixão pela Ciência, levar-te pelos caminhos das descobertas e mostrar-te como é possível transformar perguntas em soluções que melhoram a nossa vida.

A NEI no Porto, para além do i3S, que será a instituição onde irão realizar-se todas as atividades, conta com o apoio da Universidade do Porto e com a participação de mais de 15 Instituições e associações da região: Centro de Biotecnologia e Química Fina da Universidade Católica Portuguesa (CBQF); Centro de Investigação em Biodiversidade e Recursos Genéticos (CIBIO/BIOPOLIS); Centro Interdisciplinar de Investigação Marinha e Ambiental (CIIMAR); Centro de Investigação Transdisciplinar Cultura, Espaço e Memória da Faculdade de Letras da Universidade do Porto (CITCEM); Centro de Investigação de Produção Agroalimentar Sustentável (GreenUPorto); Instituto de Ciências Biomédicas Abel Salazar (ICBAS); Instituto Nacional de Saúde Doutor Ricardo Jorge (INSA); Laboratório Associado para a Química Verde (LAQV Requimte); Museu de História Natural e da Ciência/ Galeria da Biodiversidade – Centro de Ciência Viva; Museu FCPorto; Pint of Science Porto; UPTEC; Instituto Português de

Oncologia do Porto FG (IPO-Porto); e Instituto de Engenharia de Sistemas e Computadores, Tecnologia e Ciência (INESC TEC).

Saiba mais sobre o programa com todas as atividades da NEI no i3S [aqui](#). Acompanhe também todas as atualizações e informações sobre o evento no [website](#) e [redes sociais do i3S](#).

Estas atividades da Noite dos Investigadores são organizadas no âmbito do consórcio EU-EMBRACES, que é coordenado pelo [ITQB Nova](#) - Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica António Xavier e tem como parceiros o i3S e a Rede Ciência Viva - Agência Nacional para a Cultura Científica e Tecnológica.

As atividades da Noite Europeia dos Investigadores organizadas pelo ITQB Nova, em parceria com a Câmara Municipal de Oeiras, vão realizar-se na Marina de Oeiras, entre as 16h e as 22horas e juntar mais de 35 instituições científicas e clubes de ciência, assim como projetos do município e arredores. Mais informação em: <https://www.itqb.unl.pt/nei-2025>

No âmbito da Rede Ciência Viva, a Noite Europeia dos Investigadores volta ao Pavilhão do Conhecimento – Centro Ciência Viva, em Lisboa, e haverá também iniciativas em mais seis Centros Ciência Viva espalhados pelo país. Consulte aqui as atividades programadas para os vários Centros Ciência Viva: <https://nei.cienciaviva.pt/2024-2025/>

Além das iniciativas que vão decorrer no dia 26 de setembro, vão realizar-se também alguns pré-eventos que podem ser consultados [aqui](#).

Noite dos Investigadores:

A Noite Europeia dos Investigadores (NEI) é uma iniciativa promovida e financiada pela Comissão Europeia, no âmbito das Ações Marie Curie, que pretende aproximar cientistas e restante sociedade na última sexta-feira de setembro e assim partilhar um pouco o dia a dia de quem faz e produz conhecimento. Desde a sua génese, em 2005, que a NEI se tem estabelecido como um evento de referência, cativando a cada edição milhões de participantes em atividades que mobilizam milhares de investigadores entusiasmados por partilhar o seu conhecimento e os resultados da sua investigação.

A edição para o biénio 2024-2025 surge com o acrónimo **EU-EMBRACES (Empowering Minds: Boosting Research in Citizen Engagement and Schools)** - uma oportunidade para os participantes usufruírem de uma variedade de eventos cuja temática se centra nas missões da União Europeia: Adaptação às alterações climáticas; Prevenção e tratamento de cancro; Recuperação do oceano e das águas; Cidades inteligentes e com impacto neutro no clima; Transição para solos saudáveis.

Contactos:

Coordenadora

Ana Sanchez | ITQB NOVA - Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica António Xavier:
asanchez@itqb.unl.pt

Equipa de Comunicação

Adriana Costa | i3S - Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde – adrianac@i3s.up.pt

Anabela Nunes | i3S - Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde - anunes@i3s.up.pt

2 | Sponsor Kit

A Noite Europeia dos Investigadores (NEI) é um evento cultural de promoção da cultura científica destinado ao público geral. Esta celebração da ciência, que se desdobra em centenas de atividades gratuitas, decorre em simultâneo em várias cidades europeias, sempre na última sexta-feira de setembro, este ano a 26 de setembro. A edição para o biénio 2024-2025 surge com o acrónimo EU-EMBRACES (*Empowering Minds: Boosting Research in Citizen Engagement and Schools*), uma oportunidade para os participantes usufruírem de uma variedade de eventos online e presenciais cuja temática se centra nas missões da União Europeia com metas muito bem definidas até 2030.

A NEI realizou-se pela primeira vez em 2005 e, desde então, ativa a cada edição milhões de participantes e milhares de investigadores entusiasmados por partilhar o seu conhecimento e investigação. Esta é uma iniciativa promovida e financiada pela Comissão Europeia, no âmbito das Ações Marie Curie (MSCA), que pretende aproximar cientistas da restante sociedade na última sexta-feira de setembro e assim promover a troca de experiências e a partilha do dia a dia de quem faz e produz conhecimento.

nei.cienciaviva.pt
 @neieuropeiainvestigadores
 @neinvestigadores @NEI_PT
 Noite dos Investigadores

Missão

Inspirar a curiosidade e celebrar a ciência!

Na Noite Europeia dos Investigadores pretendemos criar uma plataforma inclusiva e atrativa capaz de aproximar o público da ciência. Acreditamos que a ciência é capaz de impulsionar inovação, resolver desafios a nível global e enriquecer o nosso dia a dia das mais diversas formas. Os nossos objetivos são:

- 1. Realçar a importância e o impacto da ciência na sociedade;
- 2. Promover a carreira de cientista junto dos mais jovens;
- 3. Garantir o acesso ao conhecimento e à ciência de comunidades desfavorecidas e minorias;
- 4. Demonstrar em que consiste o dia a dia de um cientista e desconstruir os estereótipos associados;
- 5. Elucidar sobre os principais benefícios que a investigação traz à sociedade;
- 6. Aumentar a confiança da população face à ciência e às entidades e pessoas que a produzem.

Sobre o evento

Website

Desde a primeira edição que a Noite Europeia dos Investigadores tem aproximado cientistas de outras cidadãs por toda a Europa. A NEI oferece uma variedade de atividades interativas, tais como:

- Experiências práticas e demonstrações;
- Workshops;
- Palestras;
- Encontros com Cientistas;
- Programa de Jovens Embaixadores;
- Debates participativos;
- Programa de Inclusão Social pela Ciência;

A NEI é um evento inclusivo e acessível a todos, atraindo um público diversificado, desde famílias e estudantes e os seus educadores, passando por todos aqueles que se queiram associar a nós na qualidade de dinamizadores de atividades. A NEI tem um impacto significativo na promoção da interação científica e no fortalecimento da ligação entre a comunidade científica e o público. Com eventos realizados simultaneamente em centenas de cidades europeias, o alcance é vasto. A NEI é, assim, uma excelente oportunidade para que empresas, associações e municípios demonstrem o seu apoio e envolvimento em iniciativas com impacto direto no desenvolvimento científico, cultural e social do contexto em que se inserem.

Mais informações sobre o evento poderão ser encontradas no [website do projeto](http://website.do.projeto).

Localidade e atividades associadas (aplicável a apolos regionais)

Em nome do consórcio EU-EMBRACES

gostaríamos de solicitar a vossa associação ao evento, fundamental para a sua concretização e sucesso. De seguida, indicaremos algumas modalidades de apoio, ainda que estejamos disponíveis para analisar e discutir outras modalidades que possam considerar pertinentes.

Modalidades

Apoiantes

Profissional ou instituição que oferece uma ajuda estratégica à concretização do projeto, nomeadamente através da prestação de um serviço, empréstimo de equipamento ou a disponibilização de um espaço.

Parceiros

Instituições que unem forças em prol de um objetivo em comum, existindo troca de contrapartidas entre as entidades envolvidas.

Patrocinadores

Instituições que investem no projeto, nomeadamente, em moldes pecuniários.

3 | Visual Materials

For ERN 2025, we adapted the materials already available during ERN 2024.

Digital banner

Social Media Template

Invitation Template

Logos

4 | Clipping List

National

- 25/09/2025 – Press Clipping – Jornal de Notícias: Prepara-te! Chegou a Noite Europeia dos Investigadores - <https://www.jn.pt/jn-tag/artigo/prepara-te-chegou-a-noite-europeia-dos-investigadores/17957990>
- 26/09/2025 – Press Clipping – Público: A ciência sai à rua na Noite Europeia dos Investigadores - <https://www.publico.pt/2025/09/26/ciencia/noticia/ciencia-sai-rua-noite-europeia-investigadores-2148663>
- 26/09/2025 – Press Clipping – Público: Noite Europeia dos Investigadores: é preciso celebrar a ciência: <https://www.publico.pt/2025/09/26/ciencia/opiniao/noite-europeia-investigadores-preciso-celebrar-ciencia-2148448>
- 26/09/2025 – Press Clipping – Antena 1: (19h) Ciência: A Noite Europeia dos Investigadores - https://www.rtp.pt/noticias/noticiario-antena1/19h-ciencia-a-noite-europeia-do-investigadores_a1_1686528
- 26/09/2025 – Press Clipping – Antena 1: (18h) Ciência: A Noite Europeia dos Investigadores - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cbsDieBkTYk>
- 12/10/2025 – Newspaper – Correio da Manhã: Noite Europeia dos Investigadores - <https://tinyurl.com/knenyvxw>
- 11/10/2025 – TV – Now: Global – Noite Europeia dos Investigadores - <https://tinyurl.com/4jhszwmc>
- 12/10/2025 – Press Clipping – Correio da Manhã: Noite Europeia dos Investigadores: a celebração da ciência junto da sociedade - <https://www.cmjornal.pt/domingo/detalhe/noite-europeia-dos-investigadores-a-celebracao-da-ciencia-junto-da-sociedade>
- 14/10/2025 – TV – Now: Global 5.0 - <https://www.nowcanal.pt/programas/global-5-0/detalhe/global-5-0-temporada-2-ep-39>

Oeiras | ITQB NOVA

- 08/08/2025 – Press Clipping – Viral Agenda: Noite Europeia dos Investigadores – Oeiras - <https://www.viralagenda.com/pt/events/1669228/noite-europeia-dos-investigadores-2025-oeiras>
- 25/08/2025 – Magazine – Oeiras Valley : Roteiro Cultural 30 Dias . Edição 265 | Setembro 2025 (page 48&52) - <https://www.oeiras.pt/documents/20124/0/Oeiras-30dias-265-web.pdf/d62149fa-7e6f-cfb2-7c0c-a9039a0582f0?t=1756130217627>
- 24/09/2025 – Radio – TSF: Agenda Cultural 30 dias em Oeiras - <https://www.tsf.pt/programa/30-dias-em-oeiras/28/>
- 26/09/2025 – Press Clipping – Cartaz Cultural de Lisboa: Noite Europeia dos Investigadores 2025 – Oeiras - <https://cartazculturalisboa.pt/evento/noite-europeia-dos-investigadores-2025-oeiras/>
- 26/09/2025 – Press Clipping – Pumpkin – Noite Europeia dos Investigadores 2025 em Oeiras - <https://pumpkin.pt/eventos/noite-europeia-investigadores-oeiras/>
- 15/09/2025 – Press Clipping – New iN -Marina de Oeiras recebe noite gratuita com magia, escape room e muitas experiências - <https://newinoeiras.nit.pt/na-cidade/marina-de-oeiras-recebe-noite-gratuita-com-magia-escape-room-e-passeios-de-barco>

Lisbon | Pavilhão do Conhecimento

- 27/09/2025 – Press Clipping – SIC – Primeiro Jornal: “Sem ciência não há futuro”: evento em Lisboa junta centenas de pessoas no Pavilhão do Conhecimento - <https://sicnoticias.pt/ciencia/2025-09-27-video-sem-ciencia-nao-ha-futuro-evento-em-lisboa-junta-centenas-de-pessoas-no-pavilhao-do-conhecimento-948b8769>
- 06/10/2025 – Press Clipping – CM TV: Falar Global – Descubra o que aconteceu na maior festa da ciência - <https://www.cmjornal.pt/cmtv/programas/informacao/falar-global/detalhe/descubra-o-que-aconteceu-na-maior-festa-da-ciencia>

4 | Clipping List

Porto | i3S

26/09/2025 – Press Clipping – Viva! O Grande Porto Online: Quer tocar nas estrelas e decifrar enigmas? Porto vive noite única de ciência viva! - <https://viva-porto.pt/quer-tocar-nas-estrelas-e-decifrar-enigmas-porto-vive-noite-unica-de-ciencia-viva/>

16/09/2025 – Press Clipping – Notícias UP: Noite Europeia dos Investigadores 2025: Ciência para todos no i3S - <https://noticias.up.pt/2025/09/16/noite-europeia-dos-investigadores-ciencia-para-todos-no-i3s/>

26/09/2025 – TV – Porto Canal - <https://tinyurl.com/a223ybc>

24/09/2025 – Press Clipping – Agenda Cultural do Porto: Noite Europeia dos Investigadores - <https://agendaculturalporto.org/eventos/noite-europeia-dos-investigadores-2025/>

17/09/2025 – Press Clipping – Viral Agenda: Noite Europeia dos Investigadores – Porto - <https://www.viralagenda.com/pt/events/1681610/noite-europeia-dos-investigadores-2025-porto>

Lagos | Centro Ciência Viva de Lagos

04/10/2025 – Press Clipping – Correio de Lagos: Centro Ciência Viva de Lagos celebra o sucesso da Noite Europeia dos Investigadores 2025 - <https://correiodelagos.com/educacao-juventude/centro-ciencia-viva-de-lagos-celebra-o-sucesso-da-noite-europeia-dos-investigadores-2025/>

01/10/2025 – Press Clipping – Mais Algarve: Centro Ciência Viva de Lagos celebra o sucesso da Noite Europeia dos Investigadores 2025 - <https://maisalgarve.pt/2025/10/01/centro-ciencia-viva-de-lagos-celebra-o-sucesso-da-noite-europeia-dos-investigadores-2025/>

30/09/2025 – Press Clipping – Diário Online Região Sul: Centro Ciência Viva de Lagos celebra o sucesso da Noite Europeia dos Investigadores 2025 - <https://regiao-sul.pt/educacao-e-ciencia/centro-ciencia-viva-de-lagos-celebra-o-sucesso-da-noite-europeia-dos-investigadores-2025/733215>

Alcanena | Centro Ciência Viva de Alviela

24/09/2025 – Press Clipping – Rádio Hertz: Centro Ciência Viva do Alviela recebe a Noite Europeia dos Investigadores este ano dedicada ao futuro da oncologia - <https://radiohertz.pt/alcanena-centro-ciencia-viva-do-alviela-recebe-a-noite-europeia-dos-investigadores-este-ano-dedicada-ao-futuro-da-oncologia/>

22/09/2025 – Press Clipping – Mais Ribatejo: Alcanena assinala Noite Europeia dos Investigadores com conversa sobre o cancro no Centro Ciência Viva do Alviela - <https://maisribatejo.pt/2025/09/22/alcanena-assinala-noite-europeia-dos-investigadores-com-conversa-sobre-o-cancro-no-centro-ciencia-viva-do-alviela/>

07/09/2025 – Press Clipping – Rede Regional - <https://www.rederegional.com/breves/noite-europeia-dos-investigadores-no-centro-ciencia-viva-do-alviela/>

06/09/2025 – Press Clipping – Mais Ribatejo: Centro Ciência Viva do Alviela celebra Noite Europeia dos Investigadores com foco na prevenção do cancro - <https://maisribatejo.pt/2025/09/06/centro-ciencia-viva-do-alviela-celebra-noite-europeia-dos-investigadores-com-foco-na-prevencao-do-cancro/>

24/08/2025 – Press Clipping – Médio Tejo: Carsoscópio promove caminhada interpretativa no Polje de Minde - <https://mediotejo.net/carsoscopio-promove-caminhada-interpretativa-no-polje-de-minde/>

5 | TV and Radio Ad Spot

Frames from the video produced for the TV Spot

FIG.1 – TEMPO MÉDIO DE VISIONAMENTO TELEVISIVO E SHARE DE AUDIÊNCIA, 2023-2024

Serviço de programa	2023		2024		Varição
	ATV	Share (%)	ATV	Share (%)	Share (p.p)
RTP1	00:35:58	11,1	00:35:41	10,9	-0,2
RTP2	00:02:51	0,9	00:03:07	0,9	0,0
SIC	00:48:11	14,9	00:47:04	14,3	-0,6
TVI	00:46:24	14,4	00:49:44	15,1	0,7
Pay TV	02:15:36	42,0	02:12:52	40,4	-1,6
Outros	00:50:50	15,7	00:57:53	17,6	1,9
Total	05:23:14	100,0	05:28:48	100,0	-

Average time of TV viewership and audience share by TV channel. Data from the 2024 regulatory report from the Regulatory Body for Social Communication (ERC)

Dates and times when ERN's 2025 advertisements were broadcast.
Data was provided by RTP, the public national radio and TV broadcaster.

Rádio e Televisão de Portugal SA

Av. Marechal Gomes da Costa, 37 1849-030 Lisboa
Tel: 21 794 7000 Fax: 21 749 7570
Capital Social: C 1.432.773.340 - N.P.C 500225680 C.R.C Lisboa

Campanha: **C25077807-NOITE EUROPEIA DOS**

Ordem de Ordem: 25006347

Canal: RTP 2	Central Compras: CLIENTES DIRECTOS / DIRECTOS
Tipo Publicidade: ESPECIAL	Distribuidor: CLIENTES DIRECTOS / DIRECTOS
Pacote: Livre	Agencia: CLIENTES DIRECTOS / DIRECTOS
Grupo: DIRECTOS	Anunciante: PAVILHAO DO CONHECIMENTO
Account: Pilar Freitas	E. Facturar: RTP - DIR. MARKETING E COMUNICAÇÃO
Período: SETEMBRO de 2025	Moeda: EUR
Valorização: DESCONTO	Tipo de Produto: OUTROS OU DIVERSOS
	Produto: CIENCIA VIVA
	Ref. Cliente: NOITE EUROPEIA DOS INVESTIGADORES -

Nr.	Material							Multi. Pro.	Dur.	Dur.Fact
S1	NOITE EUROPEIA DOS INVESTIGADORES - PAVILHÃO DO CONHECIMENTO							0,00	20	20
Dia	Cod.	Break	Mat.	Pos.	Tx. P.	Hora	Aud	Bonus	Tab	Valor Pub
Spots exibidos										
19 (6ª)	A10	RTP2 (10H00/11H00)	S1	0	0,00	10:17	-	-	T16	0,00
19 (6ª)	A15	RTP2 (15H00/16H00)	S1	0	0,00	15:35	-	-	T14	0,00
19 (6ª)	A20	RTP2 (20H00/21H00)	S1	0	0,00	20:28	-	-	T19	0,00
20 (S)	A12	RTP2 (12H00-13H00)	S1	0	0,00	12:21	-	-	T13	0,00
20 (S)	A18	RTP2 (18H00-19H00)	S1	0	0,00	18:48	-	-	T22	0,00
20 (S)	A20	RTP2 (20H00-21H00)	S1	0	0,00	20:38	-	-	T24	0,00
21 (D)	A13	RTP2 (13H00-14H00)	S1	0	0,00	14:11	-	-	T15	0,00
21 (D)	A19	RTP2 (19H00-20H00)	S1	0	0,00	19:52	-	-	T23	0,00
21 (D)	A24	RTP2 (24H00-25H00)	S1	0	0,00	24:22	-	-	T18	0,00
Spots em carteira										
22 (2ª)	A11	RTP2 (11H00/12H00)	S1	0	0,00	11:08	-	-	T15	0,00
22 (2ª)	A16	RTP2 (16H00/17H00)	S1	0	0,00	16:42	-	-	T14	0,00
22 (2ª)	A22	RTP2 (22H00/23H00)	S1	0	0,00	22:46	-	-	T25	0,00
23 (3ª)	A12	RTP2 (12H00/13H00)	S1	0	0,00	12:47	-	-	T14	0,00
23 (3ª)	A20	RTP2 (20H00/21H00)	S1	0	0,00	20:31	-	-	T19	0,00
23 (3ª)	A24	RTP2 (24H00/25H00)	S1	0	0,00	24:56	-	-	T19	0,00
24 (4ª)	A10	RTP2 (10H00/11H00)	S1	0	0,00	10:32	-	-	T16	0,00
24 (4ª)	A15	RTP2 (15H00/16H00)	S1	0	0,00	15:33	-	-	T14	0,00
24 (4ª)	A23	RTP2 (23H00/24H00)	S1	0	0,00	23:02	-	-	T20	0,00
25 (5ª)	A11	RTP2 (11H00/12H00)	S1	0	0,00	11:07	-	-	T15	0,00
25 (5ª)	A20	RTP2 (20H00/21H00)	S1	0	0,00	20:30	-	-	T19	0,00
25 (5ª)	A22	RTP2 (22H00/23H00)	S1	0	0,00	22:01	-	-	T25	0,00

Quantidade 21
Grps Reais Emitidos 0.00

Facturação

Desconto:	95,00
Total Valor Pub:	0,00
3,2% ICA (s/ total de Pub):	0,00
0,8% CINEMATECA (s/ total de Pub):	0,00
Total:	0,00

GMedia Pub - Global Media Manager
24-09-2025 15:26:46

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RTP2

Grant agreement n° 101162414

Rádio e Televisão de Portugal SA

Av. Marechal Gomes da Costa, 37 1849-030 Lisboa
 Tel: 21 794 7000 Fax: 21 749 7570
 Capital Social: C 1.432.773.340 - N.P.C 500225680 C.R.C Lisboa

Campanha: C25077807-NOITE EUROPEIA DOS

Ordem de Ordem: 25006350

Canal: RTP 3	Central Compras: CLIENTES DIRECTOS / DIRECTOS
Tipo Publicidade: ESPECIAL	Distribuidor: CLIENTES DIRECTOS / DIRECTOS
Pacote: Livre	Agencia: CLIENTES DIRECTOS / DIRECTOS
Grupo: DIRECTOS	Anunciante: PAVILHAO DO CONHECIMENTO
Account: Pilar Freitas	E. Facturar: RTP - DIR. MARKETING E COMUNICAÇÃO
Período: SETEMBRO de 2025	Moeda: EUR
Valorização: DESCONTO	Tipo de Produto: OUTROS OU DIVERSOS
	Produto: CIENCIA VIVA
	Ref. Cliente: NOITE EUROPEIA DOS INVESTIGADORES -

Nr.	Material							Multi. Pro.	Dur.	Dur.Fact
S1	NOITE EUROPEIA DOS INVESTIGADORES - PAVILHÃO DO CONHECIMENTO							0,00	20	20
Dia	Cod.	Break	Mat.	Pos.	Tx. P.	Hora	Aud	Bonus	Tab	Valor Pub
Spots exibidos										
19 (6ª)	N14	TARDE (14H00-15H00)	S1	0	0,00	14:33	-	-	T12	0,00
19 (6ª)	N19	ACESSO PRIME (19H00-20H00)	S1	0	0,00	19:15	-	-	T12	0,00
19 (6ª)	N24	PRIME (24H00-25H00)	S1	0	0,00	25:00	-	-	T18	0,00
20 (S)	N13	TARDE (13H00-14H00)	S1	0	0,00	13:58	-	-	T10	0,00
20 (S)	N18	ACESSO PRIME (18H00-19H00)	S1	0	0,00	18:15	-	-	T12	0,00
20 (S)	N23	PRIME (23H00-24H00)	S1	0	0,00	23:56	-	-	T18	0,00
21 (D)	N12	MANHA (12H00-13H00)	S1	0	0,00	12:46	-	-	T13	0,00
21 (D)	N17	TARDE (17H00-18H00)	S1	0	0,00	17:59	-	-	T12	0,00
21 (D)	N22	PRIME (22H00-23H00)	S1	0	0,00	22:43	-	-	T19	0,00
Spots em carteira										
22 (2ª)	N11	MANHA (11H00-12H00)	S1	0	0,00	11:30	-	-	T10	0,00
22 (2ª)	N16	TARDE (16H00-17H00)	S1	0	0,00	16:55	-	-	T12	0,00
22 (2ª)	N21	PRIME (21H00-22H00)	S1	0	0,00	21:30	-	-	T15	0,00
23 (3ª)	N10	MANHA (10H00-11H00)	S1	0	0,00	10:30	-	-	T9	0,00
23 (3ª)	N15	TARDE (15H00-16H00)	S1	0	0,00	15:55	-	-	T12	0,00
23 (3ª)	N20	PRIME (20H00-21H00)	S1	0	0,00	20:55	-	-	T14	0,00
24 (4ª)	N09	MANHA (09H00-10H00)	S1	0	0,00	09:30	-	-	T8	0,00
24 (4ª)	N14	TARDE (14H00-15H00)	S1	0	0,00	14:55	-	-	T12	0,00
24 (4ª)	N19	ACESSO PRIME (19H00-20H00)	S1	0	0,00	19:30	-	-	T12	0,00
25 (5ª)	N13	TARDE (13H00-14H00)	S1	0	0,00	13:55	-	-	T10	0,00
25 (5ª)	N18	ACESSO PRIME (18H00-19H00)	S1	0	0,00	18:55	-	-	T12	0,00
25 (5ª)	N24	PRIME (24H00-25H00)	S1	0	0,00	24:55	-	-	T18	0,00

Quantidade 21
 Grps Reals Emitidos 0.00

Facturação

Desconto:	95,00
Total Valor Pub:	0,00
3,2% ICA (s/ total de Pub):	0,00
0,8% CINEMATECA (s/ total de Pub):	0,00
Total:	0,00

GMedia Pub - Global Media Manager
 24-09-2025 15:27:16

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RTP3

Grant agreement nº 101162414

Rádio e Televisão de Portugal SA

Av. Marechal Gomes da Costa, 37 1849-030 Lisboa
 Tel: 21 794 7000 Fax: 21 749 7570
 Capital Social: € 1.432.773.340 - N.P.C 500225680 C.R.C Lisboa

Campanha: C25032525-Noite Europeia dos **Ordem de Ordem:** 25003551

Canal: Antena 1	Central Compras: NÃO APLICAVEL
Tipo Publicidade: INSTITUCIONAL	Distribuidor: NÃO APLICAVEL
Pacote: LIVRE	Agencia: NÃO APLICAVEL
Grupo: ANTENA 1	Anunciante: RÁDIO E TELEVISÃO DE PORTUGAL, S.A.
Account: Tiago C. Martins	E. Facturar: NÃO APLICAVEL
Período: SETEMBRO de 2025	Moeda: EUR
Valorização: VALOR	Tipo de Produto: CONF.,DEBATES,SEMINARIOS,COLOQUIOS
	Produto: Noite Europeia dos Investigadores
	Ref. Cliente: 25090139

Nr.	Material	Multi. Pro.	Dur.	Dur.Fact
S1	P - até 25/09 - Noite Europeia dos Investigadores	0,00	30	30

Dia	Cod.	Break	Mat.	Pos.	Tx. P.	Hora	Aud	Bonus	Tab	Valor Pub
Spots em carteira										
19 (6ª)	0420	BREAK 04:20	S1	0	0,00	04:20	-	-		
19 (6ª)	1015	BREAK 10:15	S1	1	0,00	10:15	-	-		
19 (6ª)	2020	BREAK 20:20	S1	0	0,00	20:20	-	-		
20 (S)	0108	BREAK 01:08	S1	0	0,00	01:08	-	-		
20 (S)	1508	BREAK 15:08	S1	5	0,00	15:08	-	-		
20 (S)	2120	BREAK 21:20	S1	0	0,00	21:20	-	-		
21 (D)	0508	BREAK 05:08	S1	0	0,00	05:08	-	-		
21 (D)	1408	BREAK 14:08	S1	4	0,00	14:08	-	-		
21 (D)	2020	BREAK 20:20	S1	3	0,00	20:20	-	-		
22 (2ª)	0440	BREAK 04:40	S1	0	0,00	04:40	-	-		
22 (2ª)	1308	BREAK 13:08	S1	2	0,00	13:08	-	-		
22 (2ª)	1640	BREAK 16:40	S1	0	0,00	16:40	-	-		
23 (3ª)	0540	BREAK 05:40	S1	0	0,00	05:40	-	-		
23 (3ª)	1340	Break 13:40	S1	0	0,00	13:40	-	-		
23 (3ª)	2020	BREAK 20:20	S1	4	0,00	20:20	-	-		
24 (4ª)	0740	BREAK 07:40	S1	0	0,00	07:40	-	-		
24 (4ª)	1420	BREAK 14:20	S1	2	0,00	14:20	-	-		
24 (4ª)	1920	BREAK 219:20	S1	3	0,00	19:20	-	-		
25 (5ª)	0420	BREAK 04:20	S1	3	0,00	04:20	-	-		
25 (5ª)	1015	BREAK 10:15	S1	2	0,00	10:15	-	-		
25 (5ª)	1840	BREAK 18:40	S1	0	0,00	18:40	-	-		

Quantidade 21
 Grps Reais Emitidos 0.00

Facturação

Desconto:	100,00
Total Valor Pub:	0,00
3,2% ICA (s/ total de Pub):	0,00
0,8% CINEMATECA (s/ total de Pub):	0,00
Total:	0,00

NOI — T — É DOS INVESTIGADORES

